

PROBE WG2 “Advanced ABL profiling” - Deliverable 2.1

Fog alerts

D2.1: Reports, white and review papers on key ABL parameters, their applications, and the end-user requirements.

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Project title (acronym)	Deliverable 2.1, Product: Fog alert
Authors	Document preparation conducted by J-F Ribaud & M. Haeffelin Authors (by alphabetical order): Quentin Laffineur, Damyan Barantiev, Luka Ravnik, Pauline Martinet, Tuononen Minttu, with additional contribution from PROBE WG2 members

1 INTRODUCTION

This section focuses on fog alerts presenting an overview of the product capabilities (accuracy, uncertainty estimates, readiness for operation etc...). Existing processing chains are also reported and published references are listed so that the reader can get more details on specific aspects if necessary.

In this section following acronyms are used:

- ALC: Automatic Lidar Ceilometer
- DL: Doppler Lidar
- MWR: MicroWave Radiometer
- DCR: Doppler Cloud Radar

2 PRODUCT OVERVIEW

Fog, characterised by low visibility due to suspended water droplets, has significant socioeconomic impacts worldwide, rivalling those of storms. Fog may be responsible for severe disruption at airports, causes road accidents, and affects various operations including rescue and military activities. In arid regions, fog serves as a vital water source. Traditional fog forecasting methods using numerical weather prediction models face challenges in accurately predicting fog onset, spread, depth, and liquid water content due to the complexity of surface-atmosphere interactions. High-resolution numerical models and large-eddy simulations offer more detailed insights but are computationally expensive. Ground-based observations and especially remote sensing measurements, complement model forecasts by providing real-time information on both fog formation and dissipation processes. These observations enhance fog forecasting accuracy, offering valuable insights into key variables driving fog life cycle.

Main instruments contributing to these alerts systems and monitoring fog life cycle processes are:

- ALC : aerosol hygroscopic growth (pre-fog conditions) and cloud base height
- DCR: fog thickness together with kinematic and microphysical properties
- MWR: thermodynamic atmospheric conditions and liquid water path (LWP)
- DL: turbulence and vertical mixing

In recent years, several algorithms have been developed to predict fog formation from observational data.

- Some make the use of artificial intelligence algorithms to forecast fog formation. Kneringer et al. (2019) and Dietz et al. (2019) devised probabilistic fog nowcasting systems aimed at predicting various low-visibility scenarios based on conventional meteorological data accessible at Vienna International Airport, with lead times ranging from +30 to +120 minutes. Heylen and Reyniers (2023) have created a neural network leveraging webcam images for the detection of fog presence or absence.
- Others, such as the one developed through the COST-PROBE action and referred to as PARAFOG, are based on inference methods (Haeffelin et al. 2016; Ribaud et al. 2021). PARAFOG relies on Automatic LIDAR-ceilometers (ALCs), visibility, and traditional meteorological information with a one-minute time resolution (<https://www.lmd.polytechnique.fr/sirta/parafog/index.html>). It provides pre-fog alerts every minute, indicating the risk of fog formation in the subsequent hour based on a fuzzy logic approach, and enables discrimination between radiation (RAD) and Stratus Lowering (STL) fog types (<https://gitlab.in2p3.fr/ipsi/sirta/parafog>). It has been calibrated using 9 years of measurements at the SIRTA observatory and 1-2 fog seasons at 5 European airports. PARAFOG presents a hit rate of ~100% for RAD and STL fog events, while the false alarm

rate is about 10% for RAD and 30% for STL. More information on PARAFOG’s documentation can be found at: <https://www.lmd.polytechnique.fr/sirta/parafog/docs/>. PARAFOG has already been successfully implemented across 6 countries (France, Belgium, Austria, Switzerland, Bulgaria, Slovenia). Note that end-users' feedback have indicated that applying PARAFOG to measurements can be challenging due to the raw file format of ALC or meteorological measurement inputs. Therefore a thoughtful consideration was made regarding the creation and utilisation of this tool. Consequently, entrusting the implementation of PARAFOG to a company such as Vaisala could prove beneficial. This decision would streamline processes for end-users, eliminating concerns about input data formats and providing them with a user-friendly interface that is both singular and straightforward (Barantiev, 2021; Ribaud, 2022).

When considering the prediction of fog dissipation, numerous processes contribute to the fog life cycle. Thus, leveraging the synergy of remote sensing measurements becomes essential.

- Todeldo et al. (2020) introduces a conceptual model for adiabatic fog, linking fog liquid water path (LWP) to its thickness, surface liquid water content, and adiabaticity. The model identifies two contributions to LWP: one proportional to adiabaticity and cloud top height (CTH), and the other to surface liquid water content and CTH. Excessive water accumulation in fog leads to the definition of two diagnostic parameters: critical LWP (CLWP) and reservoir LWP (RLWP). CLWP represents the minimum water amount causing visibility reduction to 1000 m at the surface, while RLWP is the excess water enabling fog persistence. Case studies and statistics demonstrate RLWP's positivity during fog presence, diminishing as fog dissipates.
- Dione et al. (2023) emphasises the significance of monitoring fog liquid water content and depth, alongside factors such as wind, turbulence, and temperature profiles. Additionally, diagnostic parameters like fog liquid water reservoir and adiabaticity greatly enhance the understanding of the drivers behind the fog life cycle.

Thanks to these recent results, various activities are under way for the development of tools to assess and anticipate fog dissipation.

3 PRODUCTS OVERVIEW

Products	Fog alerts
Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ALC - MWR - DCR - DL <p>Additional instruments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weather stations (T°C, RH,...) - Scatterometer sensor - Webcam images
Accuracy requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - POD for radiation fog event⁷: 87% - FAR for radiation fog event⁷: 39%
Temporal resolution Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product dedicated to nowcasting applications: ~15 minutes or less

Applications	Support nowcasting fog formation & dissipation
End-Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National weather services - Airports - Highway road services
Existing algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PARAFOG: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fog formation^{4,8,1,9}: ALC + weather station (RH) + scatterometer sensor - Fog dissipation^{10,3}: ALC + weather station (RH) + scatterometer sensor + DCR + MWR + DL - Low Visibility Procedures - LVP^{6,2}: weather station + scatterometer sensor - Automated fog detection on webcam images using machine learning techniques⁵
Assumptions needed	None
Accuracy of existing products	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) PARAFOG⁸: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Radiation fog formation: hit rate ~100% and False alarm ratio ~10% for lead times of 45min. b. Stratus lowering formation: hit rate ~100% and False alarm ratio ~30% for lead times of 45min. c. Dissipation time: on-going evaluation 2) LVP⁶: Lead times from 10 to 120 min using OLR (ordered logistic regression). Verification using RPS (Ranked Probability Score): 0.0075 at 30 min, 0.0155 by 120 min (lower score is better). 3) 3 classes (fog, no fog, undetermined) based on multiple webcams. Accuracy⁵ > 90%.
Uncertainty estimates existing?	Binary forecasts, so uncertainty is only available in terms of Skill Scores
Readiness for operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PARAFOG: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fog formation: yes

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fog dissipation: ongoing - LVP algorithm: yes - Webcam algorithm: yes
Timeliness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PARAFOG: near real-time. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Formation: 1 minute resolution updated every 5 minutes. - Dissipation: 5 minutes updated every 5 minutes. - LVP algorithm: near real-time. 10 minutes resolution. - Webcam algorithm: near real-time. 5 minutes resolution.
Data availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PARAFOG formation & dissipation: 24/7 - LVP algorithm: 24/7 - Webcam algorithm: 24/7
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PARAFOG formation & dissipation: netCDF - LVP algorithm: Unknown - Webcam algorithm: Unknown

4 REFERENCES

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